

ISSN 3026 - 8451

GAMJI JOURNAL

OF ARTS AND HUMANITIES

VOL 1 - ISSUE 1

|

JAN - JUN, 2024

A PUBLICATION OF

GAMJI INSTITUTE FOR TRAINING
AND RESEARCH

GAMJI

JOURNAL OF ARTS AND HUMANITIES

VOL 1, ISSUE 1

JANUARY – JUNE, 2024

**A PUBLICATION OF
GAMJI INSTITUTE FOR TRAINING AND RESEARCH
BAUCHI STATE,
NIGERIA
07068297660
Support@gamjiinstitute.org**

**This Journal can be cited as:
Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities, 1(1)
ISSN:3026-8451**

EDITORIAL BOARD

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

Prof. Aminu Ahmad

(Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria)

EDITORS/REVIEWERS

Prof. Bello Ayuba

(Faculty of Management Science, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria)

Samuel Muangi, PhD

(Department of Sociology, Kenyatta University, Nairobi, Kenya)

Ibrahim Alkali

(Department of Sociology, Yobe State University, Yobe, Nigeria)

Prof. Abdullahi Hassan Gorondutse

(Department of Economic and Management Science, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano, Nigeria)

Jibrin Babayo, PhD

(Department of Sociology, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Auwal Yahaya, PhD

(Department of Economics, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Jamilu Yaya, PhD

(Department of Sociology, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Yahaya Yakubu, PhD

(Department of Economics, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Yusuf Musa Yahaya, PhD

(Department of Political Science, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Auwal Kabir, PhD

(Department of Accounting, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Mohammed Inuwa, PhD

(Department of Business Administration, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Yusuf A. Yusuf, PhD

(Department of Public Administration, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Ahmad Ahmad Hassan

(Department of Sociology, University of Kashere, Gombe, Nigeria)

Magaji Dafi, PhD

(Department of Social Development, Abubakar Tatari Ali Polytechnic, Bauchi, Nigeria)

Ntongha Eni Ikpi, PhD

(Department of Sociology, University of Calabar, Cross Rivers, Nigeria)

Muktar Mohammed Aliyu, PhD

(Department of English, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

CONTENTS

Editorial Note	i
Organisational Politics and Withdrawal Behaviors: A Study of Public Universities in Nigeria	
By Abdulrahman Alkali Gaji, Muhammad Inuwa, Aliyu Ibrahim	1
The Influence of Entrepreneurial Intention On Business Start-Up Intention Among Final Year Students of Bauchi State University: The Mediating Effect of Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy	
By Emmanuel Lazarus Boyi, Muhammad Adamu, PhD	23
Appraisal of Peaceful Means of International Dispute Settlement	
By AbdulQadir Al-Ameen, PhD	40
Assessment of Public Policy Implementaton of the Public Procurement Act 2007 In The Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) Abuja, Nigeria	
By Dance, Ayuba Maikasuwa, Sylvanus Muhammed Itodo	70
Crowdfunding as The New Hope for Financing Small Business Entrepreneurship in Nigeria	
By Bukar Ali Bularafa, PhD	93
Effect of Technological Factors on Intention to Adopt Industry 4.0 Technology: The Role of Top Management Support	
By Ya’u Mudasiru Muhammed, Muhammad Adamu, PhD	118
Poverty and Food Insecurity as Disaster in Niger State	
By Umar Baba Ndeji, Mukhtar Iliyasu	149
Impact of Electricity Power Outage on Manufacturing Performance in Nigeria: A Time Series Approach (1985-2022)	
By Balarabe Inuwa Dutse, Mukhtar Iliyasu	160

EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with great pride and enthusiasm that we present the maiden edition of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities*, published by the Gamji Institute for Training and Research. This inaugural publication marks a significant milestone in our commitment to fostering academic excellence and contributing to the scholarly discourse in various fields of study.

The articles featured in this edition represent a diverse range of research topics, each offering valuable insights and advancing our understanding of critical issues. The depth and breadth of the studies reflect the dedication and scholarly rigor of the authors, and we are honored to showcase their work.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to the authors for their invaluable contributions and to the peer reviewers for their diligent efforts in ensuring the quality and integrity of the research presented. We also express our appreciation to the editorial board and support staff whose dedication and hard work have made this publication possible.

As we embark on this scholarly journey, we invite readers to engage with the research presented in this journal, to reflect on the insights offered, and to contribute to the ongoing dialogue in their respective fields. We look forward to future editions and the continued growth of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities* as a platform for academic excellence and intellectual exchange.

Sincerely,

Prof. Aminu Ahmad
Chairman, Editorial Board
Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities
Gamji Institute for Training and Research

POVERTY AND FOOD INSECURITY AS DISASTER IN NIGER STATE

By

Umar Baba Ndeji*, Muktar Iliyasu**

*Department of Economics, Niger State College of Education, Minna

+2348036207325 ubndesikudu@gmail.com

**Department of Economics, Federal College of Education, Zaria

+234 703 080 1010 iliyasumuktar@gmail.com

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12610350

ABSTRACT

Globally, food and nutrition adequacy are facing critical challenges occasioned by climate change scenarios, sharply rising food demand to falling supply, neglect of investment in agriculture, and high cost of production. All these have serious implications on rising insecurity and conflict-induced instability in many countries. Further, an increasing poverty level among the people is a stress- factor as well as a precursor of violence. The thrust of this study is to examine the implications of food insecurity, poverty and hunger. The relative deprivation theory was adopted to explain the reactions of people when they feel that there is a discrepancy between the 'ought' and the 'is' of collective value satisfaction. Data were generated using secondary sources. The paper observed that reinstalling peace and security in Nigeria can only be achieved through careful identification and proper address of causal factors. The paper recommends, among others; that there should be improved agricultural productivity through the encouragement of research and application of modern technologies.

Keywords; Food insecurity, Poverty, Disasters

1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria, a country known for its vast resources and vibrant culture, also grapples with the pervasive issue of poverty. Despite being one of Africa's largest economies, Nigeria struggles with high poverty rates that affect a significant portion of its population. The complexity of poverty in Nigeria is tangled with social, economic, and political challenges, creating a multifaceted issue that demands attention and concerted efforts. In this discussion, we will delve into the causes, consequences, and potential solutions to address the pressing problem of poverty in Nigeria.

Issues on food security was brought to limelight in 1974 during the world food meeting when it unfolded on the public authority that all countries around the world need to plan on how best to work on farming creation in order to match the per capita needs of the populace.

Metu, Okeyika, Maduka. (2016) Food security has a wide and multi-layered origination not set in turn by topographical, financial and natural variables. It hints food accessibility, food access and food use. At the start of the new millennium, through the efforts of the United Nations, world leaders assembled to look for and translate a superior approach to handling financial difficulties in 2015. Their considerations brought forth what was referred to and alluded to as Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). The first and most significant objective of the MDGs was to take out outrageous neediness and yearning; Campbell (1991). Today, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) No. 1 tries to end destitution in the entirety of its structures. In spite of the fact that MDGs made a ton of positive effects on the existence of individuals, atleast, one out of five individuals in creating districts actually live on under \$1.25 every day, and there is alarm that millions could slip once more into destitution in the event that sufficient measures are not taken. This necessitated the need for SDGs. The goal is set to address food shortage and public frailty in its second and sixteenth arrangements. Poverty and destitution keep on being difficult issues for the vast majority individuals in most emerging nations. More significantly is the complex idea of the relationship that exists between food instability and public uncertainty.

The issue of instability and the requirement for security is definitely not a new turn of events. It very well may be followed to the time when confidential responsibility for first surfaced. Additionally, what comprises public frailty as well as its causal elements varies from one individual to another. Factors that impacts our discernment about uncertainty incorporates yet not restricted to our applied models, hypothetical ideas, world view, conventional foundation, experience as well as climate. Frailty has been an exceptionally contestable idea.

Researchers like Metu, Okeyika, Maduka (2016) have seen it barely from the point of the failure to safeguard esteems recently procured. While, on a more extensive note, (Metu *et al*, 2016) suggested that to figure out instability, its direct opposite which encompasses the military and non-military dimensions as well as the people's well-being must be considered first. Effective security is central to the development of all facets of a Nation. To him, food security is a very important dimension of national security; it refers to a condition where food is available and accessible to all. Accordingly, the Nigerian government, on its own part, has not relent in ensuring national security through several arms procurement, military funding, intelligence gathering enhancement, military capacity building and logistics which is evident in the continuous rise of Defence allocation in the federal budget. However, putting a lasting end to the problems would be to identify and address its causal factors which include poverty, hunger, ill-health and inequality. The importance of these four factors has been reflected in the United Nations 2030 goals for Sustainable Development. The thrust of this paper is to examine the implications of food insecurity, poverty and hunger as a disaster.

2. CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Within the context of this research, some concepts are recurrently utilized. Therefore, in order to ensure adequate understanding of this study, its validity and reliability, the following concepts are clarified.

2.1 Poverty

The concept of poverty refers to the state or condition of lacking material resources, basic necessities, and the ability to meet essential needs for a decent standard of living. Poverty encompasses more than just a lack of income; it also encompasses deprivation in various

aspects of life, including education, healthcare, housing, nutrition, sanitation, and social support.

Poverty can be relative or absolute. Relative poverty is defined in comparison to the general living standards of society, where individuals or households have significantly fewer resources or lower income compared to the average population. Absolute poverty, on the other hand, is a more stringent measure that sets a minimum threshold of income or resources required to meet basic needs, often referred to as the poverty line.

Poverty is a multidimensional concept which points to lack of access to services, empowerment, assets and income. It is a situation where a person lacks a certain amount of possession or money. Poverty includes political, social and economic elements. The two forms of poverty are absolute and relative poverty. The former is the ability to meet one's basic needs which are food, shelter and clothing. This conception remains the same irrespective of location. While the later connotes a situation where people are unable to enjoy a required minimum level of living standards, comparing the level at which others do in the same society. Here, the location is taken into serious considerations. Many people and nations of the world today suffer from chronic poverty Garga (2015). Poverty is unavoidable in situations where there is inadequate attention to human development, agriculture and capacity building. It is a condition where people live on less than \$2 per day. But in real sense, the consequences of poverty exist on a comparative degree.

Poverty is characterized by ill being. Ill being implies a state of powerlessness, bad social relationship, insecurity, material lack, and physical weakness. Poor people are those without money and other resources required for good conditions of life, which includes good food, amenities, standards and services, which enables them to function well in their society. Poverty is the inability of people to meet up with expected level of education, life expectancy and health. The poor are not usually involved in decision making concerning the society they live in.

According to Anyanwu (1997), there are numerous factors that contribute to poverty. These factors includes inappropriate macroeconomic policies, a pause in human resource development, negative economic growth, low productivities and low wages in the formal sectors, and deficiencies in labour market as a result of limited job growth. There are more

factors leading to poverty and these factors can be categorized into ecological, economic, social, cultural as well as political factors.

Poverty has profound effects on individuals, families, communities, and societies as a whole. It restricts opportunities, limits upward mobility, and perpetuates intergenerational cycles of disadvantage. People living in poverty often face increased vulnerability to health issues, malnutrition, limited educational opportunities, and reduced access to social services. Poverty can also contribute to social unrest, crime rates, and inequality within societies.

Efforts to combat poverty involve a range of strategies, including social welfare programs, economic development initiatives, investment in education and healthcare, empowerment of marginalized communities, promotion of inclusive growth, and addressing systemic issues such as corruption and social inequality. The goal is not only to alleviate immediate suffering but also to create sustainable pathways out of poverty, enabling individuals and communities to achieve long-term well-being and self-sufficiency.

2.2 Food Insecurity

The term food insecurity can be seen from the angle of shortage in the access to nutritionally adequate and safe food resulting majorly from poverty. It is a product of inadequate consumption of nutritionally adequate food, considering the psychological requirements of food by the body as being within the sphere of nutrition and health. Chronic food insecurity is as a result of lack of resources to acquire and produce food, thereby leading to persistent inadequate diet. Food insecurity is said to exist when the demand side is not balanced with the supply side. Food insecurity exists when everyone at all times cannot afford safe and nutritious food to preserve a healthy and active life. The three pillars surrounding food security include food availability, food safety and food utilization. Departing from the aforementioned, it is noted further that food security is the antithesis of food insecurity and it exists when all people have social, physical and economic access to adequate, nutritious and safe food to meet their dietary requirement at all times. Metu, Okeyika, Maduka,. (2016) opined that, a country is food secured when there is access to food in adequate and acceptable quantity and quality, consistent with

decent existence at all times for the majority of the population. “Food hygiene and safety should also be given important consideration in order to protect the health of the people”. Sustainable food security exists when all people have social, physical and economic access to adequate, nutritious and safe food to meet their dietary requirements at all times for a productive healthy life at present as well as future.

Food security requires adequate access to basic and nutritious food that promotes wellbeing and protect every member of the society from malnutrition, hunger and starvation. In the development circle, endemic famine/drought, sudden pest attack on agricultural produce and poor yield from farmlands are threats to food security. Physical access to food, its utilization and stability are dimensions of food security. To fully understand food security, other developmental questions such as income sources, social protection, changing household structures, rural and urban development, water and inputs, retail markets, nutritional knowledge livelihood patterns, sustainable asset accumulation as well as education must be answered. There is bound to be negative impacts on the ability to identify policies to enhance personal and collective access, if these influential factors are not well understood.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This paper adopts the relative deprivation theory.

The relative deprivation theory is a sociological concept that seeks to explain how individuals and groups assess their well-being and satisfaction in relation to others around them. It suggests that people's perceptions of their own situation and level of satisfaction are influenced by a comparison with others rather than by absolute conditions alone. According to the theory, when individuals perceive a significant gap between what they have and what they believe they should have in comparison to others, they experience relative deprivation. This perception of deprivation can lead to feelings of discontent, frustration, and a sense of injustice. It is important to note that relative deprivation is subjective and based on individuals' own perceptions and reference groups.

Relative deprivation can occur in various domains, including income, wealth, education, employment opportunities and social status. For example, an individual may feel

relatively deprived if they believe that they are not receiving a fair share of societal resources or if they observe others with greater access to opportunities and resources.

The theory of relative deprivation has been used to explain various social phenomena and behaviors. It suggests that relative deprivation can lead to social unrest, political mobilization, collective action, and social movements. When individuals or groups perceive a significant gap between their aspirations and their actual circumstances, they may be motivated to take action to address this perceived injustice.

However, it is important to note that relative deprivation does not necessarily lead to collective action or social change. Various factors, such as the availability of resources, the presence of social networks, and the political climate, can influence whether individuals or groups respond to relative deprivation with collective action or adopt alternative coping mechanisms.

“The theory was first articulated by Stouffer and his colleagues to explain series of unexpected relationships between feelings of satisfaction and one's position in the army. Ted Robert Gurr, a prominent contributor to the relative deprivation theory saw relative deprivation as “the tension that develops from a discrepancy between the ‘ought’ and the ‘is’ of collective value satisfaction, and this disposes men to agitation and later violence”.

Gurr's definition explains the difference between what people ought to get or their value expectation and what they actually get and so, they are likely to agitate and then revolt when their expectations are not met. This is as a result of the fact that there are other persons who have what they are entitled to and they know getting what they want is realistic and this can only be gotten with the employment or use of violence. This is also reflected in Runciman's four preconditions of relative deprivation (of object X by person A):

- Person A does not have X
- Person A knows of other persons who have X
- Person A wants to have X
- iv. (therefore) Person A believes that obtaining X is realistic.

Deduced from the above, relative deprivation essentially means the feeling of been deprived of what one feels entitled to. The agitation for food security, poverty eradication, improvement of standard of living and the concomitant individual or group violence, robbery, kidnapping, cultism, etc which follows are quintessential cases. The extent of relative poverty, inequality, and food insecurity and the gargantuan individual and group problems resulting thereof in Nigeria have led several scholars to argue that the rationale behind the high level of insecurity in Nigeria could be traced to poverty and other factors relating to unhealthy standard of living and unstable economy. The situation of relative deprivation has led some parts of the country to graduate from peaceful agitation to violent ones, in an attempt to ensure good standard of living for its people. Food insecurity and lack of amenities for improved standard of living has created a divide in the country, where in an attempt to survive, some regions resort to claiming ownership and control of natural resources in their states. It has been argued rationally that if the reverse was the case, where there is a stable economic progress with good living standard and adequate food, there will be little or no need for resource control agitations in any part of the country, as it was in the early Nigeria. Therefore, food insecurity and poverty are issues that require urgent attention.

4. METHODOLOGY

A qualitative method of data analysis was used in this study. Data were drawn from secondary sources and analyzed for clarity, most data were gotten from online magazines, journals, newspapers, and books to evaluate the impact of poverty and hunger on Nigeria's national security.

4.1 Data Collection Method

Data for this research were collected through an extensive review of extant literature which focuses on the subject matter. The literature reviewed in this study are of high standard and reputation with data strong enough to explain the variables. Glass, 1976 noted that 'secondary data review is where you re-analyze data in order to answer the original research question in a better way or an entirely new research question with the same data to produce a good and credible research'.

5. THE DEMISE OF AGRICULTURE AND UPSURGE OF FOOD INSECURITY, HUNGER AND POVERTY IN NIGERIA

Before the beginning of colonial rule in 1900 and the discovery of oil, in the 70s, Nigeria's economy relied majorly on agriculture and was doing very well based on agriculture and trading across the borders of the country. Nigeria had enough food both for the sustenance of its population and export trade. From the 70s when crude oil was first discovered till today, there have been a diminishing return in agricultural produce as major attention has been directed towards oil exploration and revenue generation therefrom. The more attention is given to crude oil, the increase in hunger and poverty. Recently, the problem of malnourishment exists at an increasing pace in Nigeria and many other countries of the world. From agricultural exporting nation, Nigeria is now listed among the major importers of finished agricultural products. Nigeria remains a net importing nation, spending about 1.3 billion on importing food items annually. Further, Garga (2013) observed that food security problem in Nigeria is pitiable as more families face increasing level of malnourishment by the day. The Central Bank of Nigeria posited that Nigeria is yet to reach self-reliance and sufficiency in productivity. Food demand has out-grown total supply, and has attracted global attention.

Apart from the discovery of crude oil, other man-made factors contribute to the poor agricultural outputs which have given rise to poverty and hunger in the country. These factors include but not limited to ethnic and religious conflicts, policy inconsistency and corruption. While "lack of attention in agriculture brings poverty and hunger, poverty and hunger reduces people's strength to work hard to increase productivity, hence they resort to other means to carter for their needs. Food and agricultural productivity is both capital and labour intensive" and the Nigerian government is not taking things for granted, as efforts have been directed at restoring agriculture to its former status before the oil boom. Currently, agricultural output in terms of its contributions to Gross Domestic Product (GDP), could be regarded as evidence of increased concern for commitment to food security. Bello elaborated further on this, stating that Special Programme for Food Security (SPFS); Root and Tuber Expansion Programme; FADAMA Development Project; Community-Based Agricultural and Rural Development Schemes; and provision of infrastructures; among others, are food security initiatives launched by the government

to address food insecurity in Nigeria. Irrespective of these, poverty and hunger persists in Nigeria. This is mostly due to policy inconsistency and corruption in the system.

The economic recession faced by Nigeria recently and the poor agricultural output has left a large percentage of its population in extreme poverty and hunger most especially in northern Nigeria. It is worthy to note that poverty is not extremism and violence in itself; however, it (poverty) leaves people susceptible to it (extremism). For instance, the Boko Haram crisis in the Northern part of Nigeria has intensified food insecurity in the North. Many members of the region have lost touch with proper means of livelihood, living in extreme poverty and are looking for available means of survival.

6. CONCLUSION

This study examined the implications of food insecurity and poverty in Nigeria. It concluded that reinstalling peace and security in Nigeria can only be achieved through careful identification and proper address of the causal factors. It has been observed that the disaster caused on the Nigerian economy by the activities of hungry and frustrated youths is enough concerned. The demise of productivity in agriculture, due to over-concentration on crude oil, has left Nigeria with increased cases of malnourishment, hunger and poverty. Today, food demands have grown faster than total supply due to disaster, communal clashes banditry activities and the increasing cost of farm inputs. From the relative deprivation theory's perspective, there is tension that develops from a discrepancy between the 'ought' and the 'is' of collective value satisfaction. This discrepancy disposes men to agitation which results in violence. This explains the susceptibility of the poor and hungry to violence and crime. Hence the urgent need to revive the agricultural sector, return to classical governance (which provides adequately for citizens' well-being) as well as create more jobs for the youths.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The issue of food insecurity should be tackled through improved agricultural productivity, which is a function of adequate research and application of modern technologies.
2. Agricultural policies, plans and programmes should be participatory. Farmers and agriculturalist should be involved in decision making when it concerns Agricultural policies.

3. The Nigerian government should focus more on agriculture than depend solely on crude oil. This will enhance rapid attainment of food security in the country.
4. Nigeria should renew commitment to the SDGs which seeks to ensure environmental sustainability by monitoring the activities of oil-multinationals in oil producing communities to ensure that environmental hazards caused by oil spillage are reduced to the barest minimum.
5. Recent attacks by herdsmen on rural farmers in some parts of the country should be addressed immediately. This will reduce the tension faced by unarmed farmers in these regions.
6. There should be constant sensitization programmes at grass-root levels to inform the youths on the need to stay away from violence and embrace peace, no matter the level at which they believe they are deprived. However, this is possible only when the government makes adequate provisions to address inequality and marginalization in the system.

References

- Adeoti J. Economic crises in developing countries: The food dimension. *Ilorin Journal of Business and Social Sciences*; 1989
- Ajakaiye DO, Adeyeye VA. (1999) Concepts, measurement and causes of poverty. *CBN Economic & Financial Review.*;39(4).
- Anyanwu JC. (1997.) Poverty: Concepts, measurement and determinants. Proceeding of NES Conference on Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria, Department of Economics, University of Ibadan, Nigeria;
- Campbell CC (1991). *Food insecurity: A nutritional outcome or a predictor variable? Journal of Nutrition.*;12(3):403-415.
- FAO. Food Insecurity in the World: Addressing Food Insecurity in Protracted Crisis. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome; 2010. (Accessed on 25/02/2012)
- Garga E. (2015) The effects of insecurity and poverty on human development at the municipal level in the Northern Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences (JETEMS)*. 2015;6(7):268-276. Available:jetems.scholarlinkresearch.com
- Metu AG, Okeyika KO, Maduka OD. (2016) *Achieving sustainable food security in Nigeria: Challenges and way forward*. 3rd International Conference on African Development Issues;182-186.
- Mohammed H. and Kiyawa I. (Eds) (2008), *Poverty in Nigeria: Causes, Manifestations and Alleviation Strategies*, London: Adonis and Abbey Publishers Ltd. 2008; 1-7.
- Ogwumike AC. Youth unemployment: entrepreneurship development programme as an intervention mechanism. *African Journal of Business Management*, 2002; 4(6):831-835.
- United Nations (2015). *Sustainable Development Goals: 17 Goals to transform our world*.
- Von Braun, Joachin ET. *Improving food security of the poor: Concept, policy and programmes*. International Food Policy Research Institute, Washington D. C.; 1992.